

CREDIT RISK ASSESSMENT IN BANKS: MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH

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Abstract: *Credit risk assessment, monitoring, and effective loan processing are key to decision-making in banks. Advances in the field of Artificial Intelligence could help banks to improve their business decisions. In this work, we have collected publicly available data from the banking sector of the Republic of Serbia and build deep learning models on real data in order to predict loan default probability of new customers as well as the ones which have been regular in settlement of credit obligations in the previous year. The dataset consists of data from the financial statements of real economy companies as well as information on the status of companies in terms of regularity of settling their credit obligations. Results obtained in this paper show that machine learning approaches can successfully be used for credit risk assessment of companies. We have shown that using a deep learning model improves results compared to generalized linear model in terms of area of under the curve metric. In addition, our experiments have shown that using more data for training deep learning model improves performances of the model.*

Keywords: *Credit risk assessment, machine learning, generalized linear models, deep learning.*